

STUDY OF PRODUCTIVE AND REPRODUCTIVE PERFORMANCE OF LACTATING CROSSBRED (Jersey X Sahiwal) COWS

Surendra Kumar¹, Rajendra Kumar Pandey², Prashant Kumar^{3*} and Shikha Yadav⁴

1-M.Sc. (Ag.) Scholar, Department of Animal Husbandry and Dairying, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

surendrabhu49@gmail.com

2- Professor, Department of Animal Husbandry and Dairying, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005, Uttar Pradesh, India

rkpandey.bhu@gmail.com

3- Assistant Professor, Department of Animal Sciences, Sri Sri University, Cuttack-754 006, Odisha, India

prashantmksr@gmail.com

4-Assistant Professor, Department of Agriculture, Vivekananda Global University, Jaipur-303 012, Rajasthan, India:

drshikhay33101@gmail.com**Corresponding author**-Prashant Kumar, Assistant Professor, Department of Animal Sciences, Sri Sri University, Cuttack-754 006, Odisha, Indiaprashantmksr@gmail.com

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Abstract

The study was carried out to determine the different productive and reproductive parameters and their correlation with time periods (P1, P2, P3, P4, P5 and P6) and seasons (S1, S2, S3 and S4) in Crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows at Dairy Farm, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh (India). Productive and reproductive data such as body weight, lactation yield, lactation period age at first calving, calving interval and gestation period of crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows from 2010 to 2015 was collected and used for analysis with the help of SPSS (Statistical Package for social science). The overall mean of weight, age at first calving, first lactation milk yield, first lactation period, calving interval, gestation period was 421.85 ± 1.43 kg, 1662.55 ± 0.208 days, 2238.42 ± 13.69 liters, 289.23 ± 8.96 days, 399.61 ± 5.96 days, 283.27 ± 0.42 days, respectively. Cows belonging to 4th batch recorded significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher lactation milk yield of 2475.93 ± 19.65 liters in the present study. Cows born during rainy and winter seasons matured at significantly earlier age (750.18 ± 0.79 and 760.18 ± 0.18 days, respectively). Lowest age at first calving (1092.46 ± 7.47 days) was observed in cows born in winter followed by those born in rainy (1134.88 ± 6.47 days) and summer (1173.95 ± 5.89 days) seasons. It can be concluded that crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows have shown a good productive as well as reproductive performance during the present study and should be managed in such a way so that the calving interval and dry period can be reduced up to the maximum extent to enhance the lactation period and milk yield. Based on the current findings, parturition should take place during the winter season rather than summer or rainy seasons.

Key words: Milk yield, Crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cow, Lactation milk yield, lactation period, Age and weight at first calving, Weight at birth, Gestation period

Introduction-

The average milk production of indigenous cattle is very low. Milk supply for human beings has been a chronic problem in India. There can be only two ways to meet the deficit of milk production, either by increasing the livestock productivity or increasing the cattle population. More cattle population means more pressure on our already congested land. It may further cause the problems of feeds and fodder for our milch animals and the problem of adverse environmental effect due to more cattle population. In India, milk production is low due to poor genetic makeup of the livestock population, lack of efficient veterinary extension, lack of proper planning, lack of proper nutrition, low breeding efficiency, unscientific breeding, short lactation period, long inter-calving period, age at first calving and poor management practices etc.

Milk production through crossbred cattle has lead to increase the income of the farmers in almost all the regions of our country including drought prone, dry land and rain-fed areas. Productive and reproductive performance of crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows needs to be improved. Hence the present study was carried out "To investigate the productive and reproductive performance of crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows". Jersey cattle are a small breed of dairy cattle. Originally bred in the channel island of jersey, the breed is popular for the high butter fat content of milk and the lower maintenance costs. The ability to carry a larger number of effective milking cows per unit area due to lower body weight, hence lower maintenance requirements, and superior grazing ability and high fertility, high butter fat (4.84%) and protein (3.95%), and the ability to thrive on locally produced

food. Bulls are also small, ranging from 540 to 820 kg and are notoriously aggressive.

Sahiwal originated in the dry Punjab region which lies along the India-Pakistan border. Sahiwal is well known for its highest milk production and is capable to produces about 8-10 liters per day with 4.5% fat content, and average lactation period is ten month. They produce small calves (average weight of 27 kg).

Materials and Methods-

The present study was carried to estimate the productive and reproductive performance on Crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows during 2015-2016 at The Dairy Farm, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh (India).

The data for investigation were obtained from the Dairy Farm at the Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University-Varanasi 221005.

Data were recorded of 107 crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows which covered the period from (2010-2015), they comprised 321 lactation and 321 calving. The data was subjected to the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) Computer Program. The data on productive performance included calving interval, first lactation yield and lactation period, data on reproductive performance included age at first calving, weight at first calving and gestation period.

The calves are weaned at birth and hand fed milk and concentrate mixture from birth to 6 month of age, their concentrate mixture invariable included gram, groundnut cake, cotton seed cake wheat bran, salt and mineral mixture as the essential ingredients. The other locally available ingredients such as wheat, rice husk, cluster bean, black gram, crushed maize etc. where also added to the concentrate mixture as per

their availability. The proportion of protein, carbohydrates and total digestible nutrients are balanced according to the nutritional standard. The cows were fed 1.0 to 1.5 kg as pregnancy allowance during advanced gestation and 1.0 kg concentrate mixture per 3 liters of milk. The green fodder, silage and hay are produced at farm and efforts are made to provide the succulent fodder.

The calves (from birth to 6 months), 6 months to 2 years (heifer), from two year to first conception (pregnant), lactating, and dry animals are housed and cared for separately in groups. The natural service is followed and breeding bull were used and every third day vasectomies bulls were paraded for detecting lactating animals in estrus and they were allowed to roam with the heifers and dry animals to detect their heat. The following components of production and reproduction performance were taken into considerations;

1. Weight at first calving (kg.)
2. Age at first calving (days)
3. First lactation milk yield (liters)
4. First lactation period (days)
5. Calving interval (days)
6. Gestation period (days)

The data collected for the study was extended over a period of 6 years (2010 to 2015) of crossbred cows.

Grouping of the year was done as follows (Table-1):-

The whole year was grouped into 4 seasons each with a duration of 3 months based an age at first calving (Table-2).

Statistical methodology

Mean

The estimated population mean of the average value of sample as:

$$\text{Mean } (\bar{X}) = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

Where, \bar{X} = Arithmetic mean
 \sum = Summation (sigma)
 n = No. of sample

Mean deviation

$$\text{Mean deviation} = \sum \left(x - \frac{\mu}{N} \right)$$

Where, x = No. of value
 μ = Mean
 N = No. of observation

Standard deviation of mean

$$\text{S.D.} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{n}}{n-1}}$$

Where, S.D. = Standard deviation
 $\sum x$ = Arithmetic mean of the population
 x = Observation of variant value
 n = No. of observation

Standard error for mean

$$\text{S. E.} = \frac{\text{SD}}{\sqrt{n}}$$

Where, S. E. = Standard error of mean
 S.D. = Standard of mean
 n = No. of observation

Analysis of variance

The following analysis of variance was seen to test the significance of various effects (Table-3).

The analysis of variance was used to test the differences between the period and seasons against the random errors 'F' test was used to determine the significance of variance. The total variation could be due to period, season and the comparison of the mean square due to any cause with the error mean square provided for the test of significance. The comparison were made to find the ratio of the mean square concerned to the error mean square (calculated value of 'f') as compared with the tabulated value of 5 percent and 1 percent levels of probability and for different degree of freedom.

The genetic correlation and their standard error were calculated by using the formula given by Robertson (1959) as under:-

$$\text{SerG } (x y) = 1 - r^2G$$

The standard error of phenotypic correlation was obtained as stated by Snedecor and Cochran (1967).

Results and Discussion

Milk Production is the end result of a long chain of events caused by numerous and complex physiological process. It is established that many genes are involved in it and these gene each individually have either large or small effects. The frequency of which determines the animal milk yield. Genetic improvement of a population results for underlying change in the frequency of genes. Genetic forces viz. selection and gene migration are being continuously employed by animal breeder to increase the frequency of desirable gene for milk production environment may contribute as much as 75% of total variation consequently milk production has a continuous distribution between high and low relationship with

1. Weight at first calving (Kg)
2. Age of first calving (days)
3. First lactation milk yield (liters)
4. First lactation period (days)
5. Calving interval (days)
6. Gestation period (days)

Weight at first calving

The mean and standard errors for weight at first calving expressed in Table no. 4, analysis of variance have been given in Table no. 5.

The weight at first calving in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows in present investigation have been observed to be 421.85 ± 1.43 days. The present estimate for weight at first calving is higher values in comparison to report of Liaqat Ali, R.A. Gill & M. Anwar 1993.

The present estimate for weight at first calving is higher values in comparison to report by Liaqat Ali, R.A. Gill & M. Anwar, (1993).

The present value for weight at first calving showed no effect on milk yield per lactation are similar to the results were found by Nema, R.K., Tiwari, D.P. & Singh, V.P. (1996) in Jersey Holstein and Gir breeds.

The effect of period was observed to be significant on the body weight at first calving in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows. The similar effects of period were reported by Liaqat Ali, R.A. Gill & M. Anwar 1993 in jersey \times Holstein cows. The period P₂ (2011), P₄ (2013) and P₆ (2015) have higher weight at first calving than P₁ (2010), P₃ (2012), P₅ (2014) in (JS) cows.

The effect of season was observed to be non-significant of the body weight at first calving in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows. The season S₁ (Jan-March) and S₄ (Oc.-Dec.) have shown highly body wt. than S₂ (April-June.) and S₃ (July-Sep.) which is similar to the observations reported by Nema and Tiwari (1996) in Jersey- Holstein and Gir breeds.

Age at first calving (days)

The mean and standard error for age at first calving of Crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows have been detailed in Table no. 6, analysis of variance has been shown in Table no. 7.

Age at first calving for crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows in presented research work have been observed to be 1662.55 ± 0.208 days. The effects of period of calving were found to be significant level for Age at first calving in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows which is in agreement with the result of Campos *et al.* (1981), Varaprasad *et al.* (2013) in cross-bred cow. The period P₆ (2015), P₃ (2012) and P₁ (2010) shown highly significant than period P₅ (2014) and P₄ (2013) and period P₂ (2011) have significant in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows. The effect of season on age at first calving was non-significant in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows. The cows calved in season S₂ (April-June), S₁ (Jan-March) and S₄ (Oct.-Dec.) shown higher values than season S₃ (July-Sept.) in (JS) Cows. The same and higher values were reported by Lobo *et al.* (1983) and Padekar *et al.* (2002) in cross-bred Cows. It was expected that there would have been overall improvement in age at first calving due to introduction of advance animal husbandry practices and selection of superior individual.

First lactation milk yield (Liters)

Dominance and epistemic gene effects are known as non additive genetic effects and determined by genotypes rather by individual gene. During the transmission of gene from parent to offspring, these dominants epistemic combinations are break down and new combination are formed. Each generation, in contrast; additive genes effect depends on the contribution of individual genes and thus are more important in selection program in expression of gene in case of a polygenic traits, which are greatly influenced by environment factors for milk production.

The mean and standard error for the first lactation milk yield in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows have been presented in Table no. 8 analysis of variance have been given in Table no. 9.

The overall mean for the first lactation milk yield in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows was found to be 2238.42 ± 13.69 liters. The effect of period of calving were to be significant for the first lactation milk yield in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows which is in accordance with the results reported by Fayeye *et al.* (2013) & Rehman *et al.* (2008) in (JS) cow.

The effect of periods was found to be significant at ($P < 0.05$) in present research work. The period P₂ (2011), P₁ (2010) and P₅ (2014) were higher effect of overall mean and the period P₄ (2013), P₃ (2012) and P₆ (2015) were lower significant effect to the present work.

The effect off season was found to be non-significant in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows. The cows calved in season S₂ (April-June) and S₃ (July-sep.) were higher milk production. The cow which calved in season S₁ (Jan-march.) and S₄ (Oct-Dec.) shows low production of milk yield for crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows.

First lactation period (days)

The mean and standard error of the first lactation period have been shown in Table no. 10, analysis of variance have been presented in Table no. 11.

The lactation length in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows in the present research work have been observed to be 289.23 ± 8.96 days. The present value of research work for first lactation period is higher in comparison to those reported by Manavati *et al.* (1996) in (JS), Dandapat *et al.* (2010) in (JS) and Shubha Lakshmi *et al.* (2010) in Holstein x Sahiwal. The effects of period were highly significant ($P < 0.05$) on the lactation period in present research. Time period P₅ (2014), P₁ (2010) and P₄ (2013) have been shown higher in comparison of period P₆ (2015), P₂ (2011) and P₃ (2012) in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows.

The effects of season for lactation length were found to be non significant in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows. The non significant effects were those reported by Poharkar *et al.* (1996) in jersey x Holstein crossbred cows. The cows calved in season S₁ (Jan-March) S₃

(July-Sept.) S₂ (April-June) shown higher lactation length than other cows calved in season S₄ (Oct-Dec.) in (JS) cows. Similar observation reported by Manavati *et al.* (1996) in Jersey X Sahiwal.

Calving interval (days)

Scientists have defined the calving interval in dairy cattle as "the period between any two consecutive calving "and it should be 400 days for first lactation.

The mean and standard error of the calving interval of crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows have been shown in Table no. 12, analysis of variance has been presented in Table no. 13.

The calving interval in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows during the present research work have been observed to be 399.61 ± 5.96 days. The present value of research work for the calving interval is lower than the report of Reddy *et al.* (2015) in Jersey X Sahiwal.

The effects of period were highly significant ($P < 0.05$) for the lactation period in the present research. Time period P₅ (2014), P₄ (2013) and P₂ (2011) have been shown higher in comparison of period P₃ (2012), P₆ (2015) and P₁ (2010) in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows.

The effects of season on calving interval were found to be non significant in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows, which is similar to the result of Kanuya and Greve (2000) in Ayresshire cows. The cows calved in season S₂ (April-June) S₃ (July-Sept.) S₄ (Oct-Dec) shown higher lactation length than other cows calved in season S₁ (Jan-March.) in Crossbred cows. Similar observation reported by Nanavati *et al.* (1996) in Jersey X Sahiwal.

Gestation period (days)

It is the period extending from the date of conception to delivery. At optimum service period, gestation period was shown to keep the regularity of inter-calving period, hence the economical and breeding efficiency of dairy cow. The mean and standard error of the gestation period have been shown in Table no. 14, analysis of variance have been presented in Table no. 15.

Overall mean of gestation period was 283.27 ± 0.42 days in the present study. The effects of period of calving were found to be non significant for gestation period in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows. The effects of period were similar to the findings as reported by Aziz *et al.* (1994) in Jersey X Sahiwal crossbred cows. Time period P₁ (2010), P₃ (2012) and P₂ (2011) were shown highly non significant than period P₆ (2015), P₅ (2014) and P₄ (2013) in (JS) cows. The effect of season on gestation length was found to be significant at ($p < 0.05$) level in crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows which is similar to the report of Kumar *et al.* (2016) in Jersey crossbred cow. The cows calved in season S₄ (Oct-Dec.), S₁ (Jan-march) and S₃ (July-Sep.) have been shown much more gestation period in comparison to season S₂ (April-June).

Genetic correlation

The genetic correlation coefficients among various traits along with standard error of crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows are presented in Table no. 16.

There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation of weight at first calving with gestation period, weight at first calving with first lactation milk yield, similar to the report of Han *et al.* (2021), weight at first calving with first lactation period, calving interval, age at first calving, which is higher and similar to the report of Kale *et al.* (1982) in (JS) cows.

There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation of gestation period with first lactation milk yield, first lactation period, calving interval, and age at first calving which is lower and similar to the findings of Singh *et al.* (1981) in (JS) cows.

There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation of first lactation milk yield with first lactation period, which is in agreement with the result of Sawant *et al.* (2016), correlation of first lactation milk yield with calving interval, which is in accordance with the finding of Dong and

Vleck (1989), correlation of first lactation milk yield with age at first calving, which is similar to the result of Tamboli *et al.* (2022).

There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) correlation of first lactation period with age at first calving and calving interval, which is in agreement of the result of Tamboli *et al.* (2022).

Conclusions

To ensure proper economic returns, the productive and reproductive performances of crossbred (Jersey X Sahiwal) cows need to be improved. We observed that time period had a significant ($P < 0.05$) and season had a non-significant effect on weight and age at first calving, first lactation milk yield and first lactation period, first calving interval, service period of crossbred cows, respectively. The effects of season of birth and age at sexual maturity were found to have no-significant effect on lactation length. There was a highly correlation between the gestation period and first lactation milk yield, age at first calving and service period, of crossbred cows. We found that there was a negative correlation between dry period and calving interval of crossbred cows. There was a highly significant effect of batch and season of birth on the age at sexual maturity. The season of birth, batch and age at sexual maturity had non-significant influence on the gestation period. The overall mean gestation period was 276.89 ± 0.38 days. Age at first calving was significantly affected by season of birth, batch and age at sexual maturity. Lowest age at first calving (1092.46 ± 7.47 days) was observed in cows born in winter followed by those born in rainy (1134.88 ± 6.47 days) and summer (1173.95 ± 5.89 days) seasons. Mean age at first calving ranged from 911.60 ± 4.40 to 1378.37 ± 7.49 days in 1st and 4th groups, respectively.

Based on the present findings we can conclude that the crossbred cows should be managed in such a way so that maximum cows should calve during winter season to get the maximum milk yield as well as longest lactation period for enhancing the living standard of the farmer.

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Conflict of interest: None

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Table No. 1: Symbol of the years

Sl. No.	Year	Symbol
1	2010	P1
2	2011	P2
3	2012	P3
4	2013	P4
5	2014	P5
6	2015	P6

Table No. 2: Months of the seasons

Sl. No.	Seasons	Months
1	S1	January – March
2	S2	April – June
3	S3	July – September
4	S4	October – December

Table No. 3: Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

S. No	Source of variance	D.F.	S.S.	M.S.S.	F
1	Period	P-1	A	A/P-1=J	J/5
2	Season	S-1	B	B/S-1=K	K/5
3	Error				

Table 4: Mean and standard error for weight at first Calving (Kg.) in Crossbred (JS) cows

Classification	No of observations	Body Weight (Kg.)	S.E.
Overall mean (μ)	107	421.85	1.43
Periods			
P ₁ (2010)	18	410.86	3.41
P ₂ (2011)	12	426.56	5.42
P ₃ (2012)	10	421.22	4.77
P ₄ (2013)	16	424.01	5.75
P ₅ (2014)	22	420.67	6.64
P ₆ (2015)	29	427.77	5.93
Seasons			
S ₁ (Jan.-March)	19	424.96	0.492
S ₂ (April -June)	28	418.22	0.498
S ₃ (July-Sept.)	29	420.47	0.397
S ₄ (Oct-Dec.)	31	421.84	0.360

Table 5: Analysis of variance for weight at first calving in Crossbred (JS) cows

Source	DF	SS	MSS	F cal	F tab	SIG
Period	5	25595.05	5119.01	3.090141	2.901295	S *
Season	3	2416.447	805.4889	0.486241	3.287382	NS
Error	15	24848.43	1656.562			
Total	23	52859.95				

NS – Non Significant, *Significant at 5% level

Table 6: Mean and standard error for age at first Calving (days) in Crossbred (JS) cows

Classification	No of observations	Age at first calving (days)	Standard Error
Overall mean (μ)	107	1662.55	0.2081
Periods			
P ₁ (2010)	18	1664.77	2.41
P ₂ (2011)	12	1659.88	2.55
P ₃ (2012)	10	1665.32	2.51
P ₄ (2013)	16	1657.81	2.67
P ₅ (2014)	22	1662.84	2.51
P ₆ (2015)	29	1665.74	2.50
Seasons			
S ₁ (Jan.-March)	19	1664.78	0.971
S ₂ (April -June)	28	1665.34	1.027
S ₃ (July-Sept.)	29	1659.46	1.029
S ₄ (Oct.-Dec.)	31	1660.29	1.511

Table 7: Analysis of variance for age at first Calving in Crossbred (JS) cow

Source	DF	SS	MSS	F cal	F tab	SIG
Period	5	22075	4415	5.078345	2.901295	S*
Season	3	1416.833	472.2778	0.543237	3.287382	NS
Error	15	13040.67	869.3778			
Total	23	36532.5				

NS – Non Significant, *Significant at 5% level

Table 8: Mean and standard error for first lactation milk yield (liters) in Crossbred (JS) cows

Classification	No of observations	First lactation milk yield (liters)	Standard Error
Overall mean (μ)	107	2238.42	13.6921
Periods			
P ₁ (2010)	18	2482.45	59.05
P ₂ (2011)	12	2741.46	60.48
P ₃ (2012)	10	2081.77	48.40
P ₄ (2013)	16	2239.35	40.87
P ₅ (2014)	22	2449.37	61.05
P ₆ (2015)	29	1854.97	50.82
Seasons			
S ₁ (Jan.-March)	19	2144.26	2.681
S ₂ (April -June)	28	2438.72	3.241
S ₃ (July-Sept.)	29	2246.18	6.313
S ₄ (Oct-Dec.)	31	2153.44	2.74

Table 9: Analysis of variance for first lactation milk yield in Crossbred (JS) cows

Source	DF	SS	MSS	F cal	F tab	SIG
Period	5	8088526	1617705	3.283936	2.901295	S*
Season	3	3518078	1172693	2.380562	3.287382	NS
Error	15	7389175	492611.6			
Total	23	18995778				

NS – Not Significant, * Significant at 5% level

Table 10: Mean and standard error for first lactation period (in days) in Crossbred (JS) cows

Classification	No of observations	First lactation period	Standard Error
Overall mean (μ)	107	289.23	8.9659
Periods			
P ₁ (2010)	18	313.28	39.83
P ₂ (2011)	12	279.69	34.28
P ₃ (2012)	10	281.70	25.04
P ₄ (2013)	16	296.74	34.74
P ₅ (2014)	22	337.28	39.53
P ₆ (2015)	29	263.81	31.13
Seasons			
S ₁ (Jan.-March)	19	312.36	0.672
S ₂ (April -June)	28	280.42	0.504
S ₃ (July-Sept.)	29	296.28	1.357
S ₄ (Oct-Dec.)	31	272.53	1.400

Table 11: Analysis of variance for first lactation period in Crossbred (JS) cows

Source	DF	SS	MSS	F cal	F tab	SIG
Period	5	11852.33	2370.467	2.993769	2.901295	S*
Season	3	7358	2452.667	3.097584	3.287382	NS
Error	15	11877	791.8			
Total	23	31087.33				

NS – Not Significant, * Significant at 5% level

Table 12: Mean and standard error for calving interval in Crossbred (JS) cows

Classification	No of observations	Calving interval	Standard Error
Overall mean (μ)	107	399.61	5.96
Periods			
P ₁ (2010)	18	388.13	1.48
P ₂ (2011)	12	387.79	1.35
P ₃ (2012)	10	385.73	3.89
P ₄ (2013)	16	403.80	18.88
P ₅ (2014)	22	446.25	9.95

P ₆ (2015)	29	385.94	1.49
Seasons			
S ₁ (Jan.-March)	19	388.16	1.246
S ₂ (April -June)	28	429.38	0.452
S ₃ (July-Sept.)	29	402.44	1.097
S ₄ (Oct.-Dec.)	31	379.12	1.253

Table 13: Analysis of variance for calving interval in Crossbred (JS) cows

Source	DF	SS	MSS	F cal	F tab	SIG
Period	5	61170.08	12234.02	10.62357	2.901295	S*
Season	3	2321.494	773.8315	0.671967	3.287382	NS
Error	15	17273.87	1151.591			
Total	23	80765.45				

NS – Not Significant, *Significant at 5% level

Table 14: Mean and standard error for gestation period in Crossbred (JS) cows

Classification	No of observations	Gestation period	Standard Error
Overall mean (μ)	107	283.27	0.4290
Periods			
P ₁ (2010)	18	284.39	1.73
P ₂ (2011)	12	284.19	1.77
P ₃ (2012)	10	284.32	1.88
P ₄ (2013)	16	281.56	2.11
P ₅ (2014)	22	282.18	2.29
P ₆ (2015)	29	283	2.62
Seasons			
S ₁ (Jan.-March)	19	284.22	0.411
S ₂ (April -June)	28	281.84	0.611
S ₃ (July-Sept.)	29	282.96	0.500
S ₄ (Oct.-Dec.)	31	284.53	0.411

Table 15: Analysis of variance for gestation period in Crossbred (JS) cows

Source	DF	SS	MSS	F cal	F tab	SIG
Period	5	10.375	2.075	1.106667	2.901295	NS
Season	3	42.125	14.04167	7.48889	3.287382	S*
Error	15	28.125	1.875			
Total	23	80.625				

NS – Not Significant, *Significant at 5% level

Table No. 16: Genetic and phenotypic correlation among different reproductive traits of Crossbred (JS) cows

Particular	Weight at first calving	Gestation period	Lactation yield	Lactation period	Calving interval	Age at first calving
Weight at first calving	1					
Gestation period	0.70315	1				
Lactation yield	0.66444	0.853061	1			
Lactation period	0.61493	0.581744	0.464096	1		
Calving interval	-0.004	-0.17284	0.091401	0.40942	1	
Age at first calving	0.449603	-0.21364	0.01715	0.18128	0.652553	1